

A HIGH HEAT-RESISTENCE THERMOSETTING RESIN SYSTEM BASED ON NOVOLAK AND BISMALIMIDE FOR RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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SUMMARY: The optimum composition of bismaleimide/allylated novolak resin system (BMAN), especially with lower bismaleimide (BMI) content, were founded after the detail discussion for the effects of molecular weight of novolak, allylation degree of novolak and the amount of BMI on the heat-resistance and viscosity of BMAN resin system. It is important for the BMAN with high heat resistance and good RTM processability resin for RTM to possess a proper molecular weight of novolak, and high allylation degree as possible. The viscosity of BMAN is still less than 0.4Pa.s after 8h at 110°C. The resin system showed no T_g before its heat decomposition above 400°C, indicating an ideal cross-linked network was formed in their curing state. BMAN/quartz cloth composite showed high flexural modulus retention rate up to 90.7% at 350°C.

Mechanism of the curing reaction was also discussed. From results of FT-IR, a reasonable explain is that O-allylated allyl group turned C-allylated allyl group via Claisen rearrangement reaction firstly, and then reacted with BMI to form a conjugated diene structure, and the diene reacted with residual allyl groups via Diels-Alder reaction to form a hexatomic ring networks.

KEYWORDS: resin transfer moulding, novolak, bismaleimide, high heat-resistance

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) for the fabrication of composite materials is receiving more and more attention because of its comparatively low cost and high efficiency[1,2]. The resins for RTM should have a long pot life and low viscosity (<0.5pa*s) at the injection temperature, fast curing capacity at process temperature, good adhesion between the resin matrix and reinforcements and a low curing shrinkage. In addition, as a resin matrix of high performance composites, outstanding strength, module and thermo-oxidative stability were needed. Traditional high-performance resins, such as polyimide and phenolic resins, did not adapt to the requirements of RTM process due to their high viscosities, high solvent contained and high volatile substance emitted when cured. Special method were used for RTM composites based on phenolic resin matrix[3-5]. Recently, a thermosetting resin system based on novolak and bismaleimide (BMI) has been developed in our laboratory.[6,7]. In this system, novolak resin was allylated, and then BMI was introduced as coreactant. The resins have good thermal and mechanical properties and can be processed using RTM technology.

It was widely accepted that upon the curing reaction of BMI-allyl novolak system, BMI reacts with allyl group via "Ene" reaction firstly, and then, Diels-Alder reactions occurred at higher temperature to form ring structure [8-11]. These processes were shown in **figure 1**.

Figure 1. Curing of of BMI/Allylated-novolak via Ene/Diels-Alder reaction

In order to improve further thermo-mechanical properties of the resin system, three key factors should be considered: (1) the allylation degree of novolak, (2) the molecular weight of novolak and (3) the amount of BMI. The objective of this work is to determine how the allylation degree, the molecular weight of novolak and the amount of BMI affect the heat-resistance capacity of the BMI-allylated novolak (BMAN) resin system and to select some recipes fitted for RTM process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Phenol (CP) and formaldehyde (37% solution in water, CP) were obtained from the Beijing Organic Chemicals Factory and used as supplied. Allyl chloride was obtained from Qilu Petrochemical Co. Ltd. and used after distillation. 4,4-Bismaleimidodiphenylmethane (BMI) was purchased from Fengguang Chemical Co. Ltd, and used as supplied.

Syntheses of novolak and allylated novolak resins were referred to our former works [6]. Molecular weight of novolak resins and allylation degree of allylated novolak resins were determined by ^1H NMR.

Preparation of BMI/allylated novolak resin systems (BMAN) were carried out as follow: allylated novolak resin was heated to 130• to 140• in a three-naked bask by an oil bath firstly, and then BMI was added and stirred evenly. When the system turned transparent, the mixture was kept at the temperature and then the reaction was ended after a few minutes. The molar of BMI was changed in a wild range from 10 % to 50% of the molar of allyl groups

Figure 2 preparation of BMAN resin

Preparation of cured BMAN

The performed polymer of BMAN was placed in a steel mould and desolvented in vacuum oven at 130• for 3 h, and then cured at 170•/2h, 200•/6h and 250•/6h.

Measurements

The T_g values of the cured BMAN resins were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 7 dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) instrument with a force of 1.00Hz at a heating rate of 5•/min. Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) were carried by a Perkin-Elmer 7 series instrument at a heating rate of 20•/min.

^1H NMR and FT-IR were used to analyze the structure of materials. Novolak and allylated novolak were solute in D-substituted DMSO, and analyzed by a DMX-300 NMR instrument. FT-IR analysis were taken by a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR 2000 instrument.

Viscosity was measured on a NDJ-79 viscometer at different temperature, and the values were noted every 1 hour.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Effects of molecular weight and allylation degree of novolak on heat-resistance

In order to determine an appropriate molecular weight and allylation degree of novolak, a series of experiments were designed as shown in Table 1. As allylated novolak resins with higher allylation degree could not reacted with BMI at a mole ratio of 0.50 of allyl groups to form homogenous resin system in our experiment, so another loewer molar ratio of 0.37 were chosen.

Table 1 BMAN resins synthesized with different molecular weight and allylation degree

Code	Molecular weight of novolak	Allylation degree	Mole ratio of BMI : allyl group
BMAN1	345	65.32%	0.50
BMAN2	345	84.36%	0.50
BMAN3	345	97.07%	0.37
BMAN4	425	69.87%	0.50
BMAN5	425	83.40%	0.50
BMAN6	425	100.00%	0.37
BMAN7	488	75.70%	0.50
BMAN8	488	82.37%	0.50
BMAN9	488	100.00%	0.37

Heat-resistance ability of the BMAN resins was characterized by five indexes, including T_g , T_{onset} , modulus maintenance at T_g , modulus maintenance at T_{onse} and modulus maintenance at 350•. These indexes were determined by DMA and listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Heat-resistance ability of BMAN resins

Code	T_g (•)	T_{onset} (•)	modulus maintenance at T_{onse}	modulus maintenance at 350•	modulus maintenance at T_g
BMAN1	366.91	312.50•	60.71%	35.71%	16.07%
BMAN2	379.60	337.10•	59.92%	48.99%	33.20%
BMAN3	392.35	327.00•	68.59%	60.65%	28.88%
BMAN4	390.78	305.00•	51.60%	30.40%	42.90%
BMAN5	399.93	333.00•	10.27%	57.79%	19.01%
BMAN6	386.65	315.00•	73.08%	50.00%	15.38%
BMAN7	389.33	315.00•	73.08%	50.00%	15.38%
BMAN8	402.27	337.50•	75.47%	71.70%	22.64%
BMAN9	396.52	353.00•	74.80%	73.40%	26.10%

It could be concluded from Table 1 that specimen with high molecular weight and high allylation degree showed the best heat-insistence ability. The heat-resistance ability of BMAN was mostly relied on the molecular weight of novolak, in other words, the length of the novolak chain, and allylation degree of allylated novolak.

2. Influence of amount of BMI to heat-resistance ability and process ability

The amount of BMI was important for the heat-resistance and rheology properties to BMAN. At higher allylation degree, it was found that BMI tend to deposit at 0.50 molar ratio of allyl groups, and less BMI, i.e. 0.37 molar ration of allyl groups was chosen to prepare BMAN in experiments. In Table 1, though less BMI were used for BMAN3, BMAN6 and BMAN9, their thermo-resistance did not decreased. It seemed that at higher allylation degree, the BMI could be used at lower amount to prepare BMAN without sacrifice their thermo-resistance. Furthermore, less BMI amount will facilitate the viscosity of the system, which is more suitable for the process of RTM. So a series of experiment were carried to study the influence of amount of BMI to heat-resistance ability and RTM processabilities.

For acquiring better heat-resistance ability we choose an allylated novolak resin which allylation degree was 118%. The molecular weight of the novolak was still 488. The molar ratio of allyl groups:BMI was decreased from 1:0.30 , 0.25, 0.20 to 1:0.15. Heat-resistance ability of the BMANs was listed in Table3.

Table 3. Heat-resistance property of BMANS with different BMI content

Code	Molar ratio of allyl group:BMI	$T_g(\cdot)$	$T_{onset}(\cdot)$	modulus maintenance at 350 \cdot	modulus maintenance at T_{onse}	modulus maintenance at T_g
BMAN10	1:0.30	417.47	375.11	79.73%	68.02%	21.62%
BMAN11	1:0.25	409.01	369.24	76.70%	67.96%	32.53%
BMAN12	1:0.20	406.59	364.79	77.73%	67.21%	27.94%
BMAN13	1:0.15	418.63	390.63	87.60%	70.66%	35.12%

It was shown in Table 3 that the heat-resistance of high-allylated BMANs have no obvious change with the decrease of BMI. It means the amount of BMI could be properly decreased without worrying about heat-resistance. In fact, by reducing the amount of BMI, we found a series of BMAN adapt to RTM process. The adaptable ability of BMAN for RTM was characterized by observation of viscosity changes at process temperature in a long time. Viscosity-time curves at 110 \cdot of some BMAN resins were shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Viscosity of BMAN resins

In Figure 3 some resins, such as BMAN12 and 13, showed well adaptable ability for RTM process. In a conclusion, reducing amount of BMI benefits adaptable ability of BMAN for RTM, and heat-resistance property is not negatively affected. The fact leads to a heart-stirring prospect for designing high heat-resistance resin which is facility to RTM process.

3. Study of curing process of BMAN with low BMI content

BMAN13 was chosen to study the curing process. Its allylation degree is 117.90% and most of hydrogen atom in hydroxyl group was substituted by allyl group. The FT-IR spectrum of the allylated novolak of BMAN13 was shown as Figure 4.1. and spectrum of the novolak which molecular weight

is 488 was shown as Figure 4.2. BMAN13 performer was spread on a piece of KBr, and treated at 170•, 2h, 200•, 6h and 250•, 6h in a vacuum oven. FT-IR spectrums of every treating step were shown in Figure 4.3. The curve marked 1, 2, 3 and 4 were IR spectrum of performer, treated at 170• after 2 hours, at 200• after 6 hours and at 250• after 6 hours respectively.

Figure 4.1. FT-IR spectrum of allylated novolak **Figure 4.2. FT-IR spectrum of novolak**

Figure 4.3. FT-IR spectra of BMAN 13 for curing process

In the curing process some obvious changes of peaks were observed. First, the peak of O-H• was stronger and stronger with heating treatment. In the spectrum of the performer, it is a weak, sharp peak at 3474.14cm^{-1} , when treated at 170• after 2 hours, it changed into a middle peak, and showed a character of hydrogen bond. After treated at 200• in 6 hours, the peak turned to a strong hydrogen bond peak. The second, peak at 1242.62cm^{-1} in curve 1, which was contributed to a C-O bond of phenyl originally, had obvious changes in the treating process. When treated after 170•, 2h, it divided into two peaks. One still keep the position at 1242cm^{-1} . The other, appears at 1180cm^{-1} . After treated at 200•, the peak 1242cm^{-1} weakened obviously and amalgamated into the peak at 1180cm^{-1} in a great measure. After treated at 250•, only peak at 1180cm^{-1} could be seen clearly. The third, aromatic C-H vibration peak at 3010cm^{-1} turned weaker and weaker in the process, so did characteristic peaks of allyl group at $990, 910\text{cm}^{-1}$ and the characteristic peak of phenolic aldehyde resin at about 810cm^{-1} . From figure 4 we can conclude that after treated at 200• and 250•, the strength of the characteristic

peak of allyl group and benzene ring was waken obviously. At the same time, the position of the characteristic peaks of O-H hydrogen bond appears at a higher wavenumber (about 3474cm^{-1}) than either that of phenol (multi-substituted, such as novolak, at 3310cm^{-1}) and aliphatic alcohol (about 3300cm^{-1}). The position could be explained by enol structure as **b** or **a** shown in figure 5. The structure could only be formed by Diels-Alder reaction occurred between conjugated diene and monoene, including not only BMI but also allyl group. Because BMI was so little and allyl group and benzene ring were reduced heavily, most consumed allyl groups must not react with each other but participate in Diels-Alder reaction with the diene crated by ene reaction. This would benefit to the heat-resistance capacity of BMAN because it creates multi-hexatomic rings. The changes mentioned above should be contributed mainly to some reactions shown in **Figure 5**:

Figure 5. Proposed reactions occurred in curing process

The Claisen rearrangement reaction (reaction 1) is a very important reaction to the heat-resistance ability of BMAN. This result was not only contribute to the reaction generates a C-allylated structure which could react with BMI to create a conjugated diene, but also eliminates ether bond, which was considered an easily decomposing structure. Conjugated diene structure was formed, as widely accepted, mainly by ene reaction between allyl groups and BMI. When the conjugated diene structure reacted with allyl groups in another novolak chain by Diels-Alder reaction, a hexatomic ring was formed and the two novolak chains were connected. The reaction occurs continually until most of reactionable groups transformed to the hexatomic structure and a very dense cured resin was formed.

4. Design and characterization of BMAN resin with good RTM processability and high heat-resistance

As we have discussed for BMAN resin systems, molecular weight of novolak, allylation degree of novolak and the amount of BMI effect their heat-resistance and process property for RTM. Molecular weight of novolak should be high enough to avoid too much faults in the network of cured resin, but if it is too high, viscosity of the BMAN performer would increase rapidly and the resin could not adapt the request of RTM process. Increasing of allylation degree should enhance the network density of cured BMAN. High allylation degree ensured BMAN resin possess a low viscosity at process temperature. The amount of BMI should be controlled at a low level so that the BMAN resin possesses a good process property.

Some high heat resistance BMAN resins adapting to RTM process had been prepared in our laboratory. Performance of one of the resins was shown as following. Figure 6 showed a viscosity-time curve of the BMAN in eight hours at 100°. It is very clear that the viscosity have no obvious increase and still maintain a low viscosity value of 200~300 mpa.s. The result showed a good process ability for RTM

Figure 6. Viscosity-time curve of BMAN resin Figure 7 DMA curve of cured BMAN

Figure 7 is the DMA curve of the cured BMAN resin cast-moulding. It showed heart-stirring heat resistance ability. The modulus maintenance at 350° was quit high. The glass transition temperature obtained by tgδ transition was more than 420°. Figure 8 is the TGA curve of the cured BMAN moulding powder. The onset temperature of heat decomposition was about 410°. It seemed the BMAN had no Tg before its heat decomposition, indicating the cured resin had an ideal cross-linkage network

Figure 8 TGA curve of cured BMAN

Property of BMAN/quartz cloth composite was measured at room temperature, 300° and 350°, and flexural strength and Flexural modulus was shown in Table 4. It showed the composite had a high flexural modulus retention rate up to 90.7% at 350°.

Table 4. Properties of composites based on BMAN/quartz cloth

Property	Value	Maintenance
Resin Content (wt)	33.1%	
Flexural strength (MPa)		
25°	365	
300°	232	63.6%
350°	199	54.5%
Flexural modulus (GPa)		
25°	18.2	
300°	17.5	96.2%
350°	16.5	90.7%

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CONCLUSION

A series of BMAN resins for RTM were designed and prepared. The resins showed high heat-resistance and good process ability. Some parameters were discussed. The conclusions were that it is important to a high heat resistance BMAN resin for RTM to possess a proper molecular weight of novolak, and high allylation degree as possible. The amount of BMI, was not necessarily maintain a molar ratio with allyl group of 0.5:1. We can reduce the amount of BMI properly to improve process performance of BMAN.

Mechanism of the curing reaction was discussed. From results of FT-IR, a reasonable explain is that O-allylated allyl group turned C-allylated allyl group via Claisen rearrangement reaction firstly, and then reacts with BMI to form a conjugated diene structure. Most of the diene reacts with residual allyl groups via Diels-Alder reaction to form a hexatomic ring networks.

REFERENCES

1. W.M.Lee and G. A.Laman, *37th International SAMPE Symposium*, 679(1992).
2. J.Hanchen, *Fiber Reinforced Composites* 2, 1(1992)
3. J.Sticklen, et al., *Tutorial on Polymer Composites Molding; Intelligent Systems Laboratory, Michigan State University, USA*, 1999.
4. J.A.Grande, *Modern Plastics*, 7, 36(1995).
5. L.B.Manfredi, J.M.Kenny, A.Vázquez, et al., *Polymer Composites*, 5, 675(1999).
6. Y.H.Yan, X.M.Shi, J.G.Liu, T. Zhao and Y.Zh.Yu, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 83, 165 (2002)
7. Y.H.Yan, L.J.Zhi, H.Sh.Wang, J.G.Liu, T.Zhao and Y.Zh.Yu, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 86,1265 (2002)
8. H.D.Stenzenberger, P.König, W.Romer, S.Pierce and M.S.Canning, *29th National SAMPE Symposium*, 1043(1984).
9. H.D.Stenzenberger, P.König, W.Romer, S.Pierce and M.S.Canning, *32nd International SAMPE Symposium*, 44(1987),.
10. M.A.Chaudhari and J.J.King, *SME Conference*, 503(1985).
11. J. J.King, M.Chaudhari and S.Zahir, *29th National SAMPE Symposium*, 392(1984).
12. C.P. Reghunadhan Nair, *J. Scientific & Industrial Research*, 61, 17(2002).